

the synthesis of uridylyl-(5'-3')-adenosine (6) has been reported (Scheme 1). 5'-O-Dialkylphosphinothiouridine could not be prepared selectively in pure form by reacting uridine (2) with an equimolar

amount of dialkylphosphinothiobromide (1) under different reaction conditions but a mixture of mono-, di- and tri-substituted derivatives was obtained. The selective activation of the 5'-position of similar nucleoside triesters is known^{8,9}.

Uridine on reaction with dialkylphosphinothiobromide (1) in pyridine afforded 2',3',5'-O-tris-dialkylphosphinothiouridine (3a-c) in 78-82% yield. Alongwith this nucleoside triester, traces of monoester and diester were also detected in the reaction products by chromatography. The elemental analysis and ir spectra were in conformity with the structure. 2',3',5'-O-Tris-dialkylphosphinothiouridine (3a-c) when reacted with adenosine 3'-phosphate (4) in pyridine in the presence of silver acetate gave 2',3'-O-bis-dialkylphosphinothiouridylyl-(5'-3')-adenosine (5a-c) in 50-65% yield. 2',3'-O-Bis-dialkylphosphinothiouridylyl-(5'-3')-adenosine (5a-c) on hydrolysis with methanolic ammonia afforded uridylyl-(5'-3')-adenosine (6) in 50-55% yield. The structure was confirmed on the basis of its uv, ir, elemental analysis, co-tlc and co-pc with the authentic sample.

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to Prof. P. C. Gupta for useful suggestion and to Dr. (Mrs.) K. Misra

for her guidance. The financial assistance by C.S.I.R., New Delhi, is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. T. HATA, Y. MUSHIKA and T. MUKAIYAMA, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 4532; *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1970, **40**, 3505; *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1971, **44**, 232; R. WHITMANN, *Chem. Ber.*, 1963, **96**, 2116; F. GAMER, R. WHITMANN, K. DANKEK and G. WEISMANN, *Angew. Chem.*, 1963, **75**, 92.
2. A. KORNBERG, "DNA Synthesis", Freeman, San Francisco, 1974.
3. H. G. KHORANA, *Harvey Lect. Ser.*, 1968, **62**, 79; R. LOHRMANN, D. SOLL, H. HAYATSU, E. OHTSUKA and H. G. KHORANA, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 819.
4. K. L. AGARWAL and T. YAMADA, *Nature (London)*, 1970, **227**, 27; C. L. HARVELY, K. OLSON, A. D. OZEKALA and A. L. NUSSBAUM, *Nucl. Acid Res.*, 1975, **2**, 200; H. KOSTER, H. BLOCKER, R. FRANK, G. BRUSSENHAINER, W. KAISER and H. SEYLER, *J. Physiol. Chem.*, 1975, **250**, 4592; J. STAWINSKI, T. T. HOZUMI, S. A. NARANG, C. P. BAHL and R. WU, *Nucl. Acid Res.*, 1977, **4**, 353; R. H. SCHELLER, R. E. DICKSON, H. W. BOYER, A. D. RIGGS and I. ITAKURA, *Science*, 1977, **196**, 177.
5. J. J. FOX, K. A. WATANABLE and A. BLOCK, *Prog. Nucl. Acid Res. Mol. Biol.*, 1966, **5**, 251; I. D. JENKINS, J. P. VERHEYDEN and J. G. MOFFATT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **98**, 3346; R. D. SIDWELL, J. H. HYFFMAN, G. P. KHARE, L. B. ALLEN, J. T. WITKOWSKI and R. K. ROBINS, *Science*, 1972, **177**, 705; E. FANLAND, W. KAMPL, M. THIEL, K. DIETMANN and W. JUERAN, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1972, **76**, 113; M. I. LIM, W. Y. REN, B. A. OTTER and R. S. KLEIN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1983, **118**, 780.
6. R. LOHRMANN and H. G. KHORANA, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 829.
7. R. L. LETSINGER and K. K. OGILVIE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 4801.
8. T. HATA and K. MISRA, Research Report Submitted to Tokyo Institute of Technology International Post-Graduate University Course in Chemistry and Chemical Engineering, 1971-72.
9. S. AGARWAL and K. MISRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1980, **19**, 132.
10. O. A. HANES and F. A. ISCHERWOOD, *Nature (London)*, 1949, **164**, 1107.
11. R. S. BAUDWIKI and N. AXELROD, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1951, **193**, 405.
12. H. S. BOOTS and C. A. SHABRIGHT, *Inorg. Synth.*, 1946, **2**, 153.
13. L. MAIER, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1964, **47**, 190.

Synthesis of 3-Substituted-aminopropoxy-2'-hydroxycoumarin Derivatives as Possible β -Blockers

S. M. DESAI and K. N. TRIVEDI*

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, M. S. University of Baroda, Baroda-390 002

Manuscript received 26 July 1988, revised 24 January 1989, accepted 31 March 1989

PROPRANOLOL, a well-known β -adrenergic blocking drug, was first introduced for the treatment of angina and later found to possess significant anti-hypertensive activity¹. It is therefore hoped that the compounds 3, prepared by attaching β -blocking sidechain to 7-position of coumarin ring system may

produce antihypertensive effect. We report here the synthesis of various propanolamine containing substituted coumarin derivatives.

7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (1) on treatment with epichlorohydrin in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate and dimethylformamide gave 7-(2,3-epoxypropoxy)-4-methylcoumarin (2) and a dimer bis-1,3-(4'-methyl-7'-coumaryloxy)propan-2-ol.

2-ol. These dimers (2b) are also of interest as they are analogues of chromoglysic acid. Condensation of 2a with isopropylamine in refluxing ethanol furnished 4-methyl-7-(3-isopropylamino-2-hydroxypropoxy)coumarin in good yield. Similarly, all other compounds were synthesised. The compounds were characterised by their analytical and spectral data.

Experimental

The following general methods were used to prepare the compounds (Table 1).

4-Methyl-7-(2,3-epoxypropoxy) coumarin (2) : A mixture of 4-methyl-7-hydroxycoumarin (1; 1.76 g), epichlorohydrin (20 g) and dimethyl formamide (10 ml) was heated in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate on a steam-bath for 8 h. The reaction mixture was then poured in ice-cold water and filtered. Tlc revealed presence of two compounds, hence it was subjected to the column chromatography. The column when eluted with benzene yielded 4-methyl-7-(2,3-epoxypropoxy)coumarin, crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether, (0.6 g), m.p. 138°, and the column when eluted with benzene-methanol yielded a dimer 1,3-(4-methyl-7-coumaryloxy)propan-2-ol, crystallised from methanol, (0.7 g), m.p. 188°; δ 2.4 (3H, s, CH₃, at position-4), 2.6-2.95 (2H, m, -OCH₂CH-CH₃),

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	R ¹	R ²	R ³	R ⁴	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
2a	H	OH ₂	H	—	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₄	193	50
2b	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	—	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₄	148	60
2c	H	C ₆ H ₅	H	—	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₄	195	60
2d	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	H	—	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ O ₄	152	60
3a	H	Me	H	NHCHMe ₂	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ O ₄ N	138	70
3b	H	Me	H	C ₄ H ₉ NO	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ O ₄ N	96	65
3c	H	Me	H	C ₁₀ H ₁₅ N ₂	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ O ₄ N ₂	150	60
3d	H	Me	H	C ₇ H ₁₀ N	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ O ₄ N	95	60
3e	H	Me	H	C ₄ H ₁₀ N	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ O ₄ N	85	65
3f	H	Me	Me	C ₈ H ₁₀ N	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ O ₄ N	105	70
3g	H	Me	Me	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ N ₂	C ₂₄ H ₂₉ O ₄ N ₂	163	70
3h	H	Me	Me	NHCHMe ₂	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ O ₄ N	130	70
3i	H	Me	Me	C ₄ H ₉ NO	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ O ₄ N	110	75
3j	H	Me	Me	C ₄ H ₉ N	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ O ₄ N	180	60
3k	H	Me	Me	N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂ HCl	C ₁₉ H ₂₅ O ₄ HCl	160	60
3l	H	Ph	H	NOHMe ₂	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ O ₄ N	129	70
3m	H	Ph	H	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ N ₂	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ O ₄ N ₂	105	70
3n	H	Ph	H	C ₄ H ₉ NO	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ O ₄ NHCl	170	70
3o	H	Ph	H	C ₈ H ₁₀ N	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ O ₄ N	128	60
3p	H	Ph	H	C ₄ H ₉ N	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ O ₄ N	102	60
3q	Ph	Ph	H	C ₈ H ₁₀ N	C ₂₉ H ₃₃ O ₄ N	175	65
3r	Ph	Ph	H	NHCHMe ₂	C ₂₇ H ₂₇ O ₄ N	150	70
3s	Ph	Ph	H	N(OH ₂) ₂	C ₂₉ H ₂₉ O ₄ N	166	70
3t	Ph	Ph	H	N(N ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₉ H ₂₉ O ₄ N	128	75
3u	Ph	Ph	H	N(O ₂ H ₄ OH) ₂	C ₂₉ H ₂₉ O ₆ N	132	75
3v	Ph	Ph	H	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ N ₂	C ₃₄ H ₃₇ O ₄ N ₂	175	70
3w	Ph	Ph	H	C ₄ H ₉ N	C ₂₉ H ₃₃ O ₄ N	175	75
3x	Ph	Ph	H	C ₄ H ₉ NO	C ₂₉ H ₃₃ O ₄ N	182	70
4a	H	CH ₃	H	—	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₇ H ₂ O	188	40
4b	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	—	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ O ₇ H ₂ O	200	40
4c	H	C ₆ H ₅	H	—	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ O ₇ H ₂ O	245	40

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

3.35 (1H, m, $-\text{OCH}_2-\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2$), 3.95 and 4.3 (1H_A, dd, J 12, 5 Hz and H_B, dd, J 12, 2 Hz, of $-\text{O}-\text{C}(\text{H}_A)-\text{CH}(\text{O})-\text{CH}_2(\text{H}_B)$), 6.1 (1H, s, proton at position-3), 6.8 (1H, s, at position-5) and 7.3–7.55 (2H, m, proton at position-7 and -8).

4-Methyl-7-(2-hydroxy-3-isopropylaminopropoxy) coumarin (3): A mixture of 4-methyl-7-(2,3-epoxypropoxy)coumarin (1.0 g) and isopropylamine (1 ml) in methanol was refluxed for 6 h on a steam-bath. The solvent was then evaporated to afford 3 which was crystallised from benzene–petroleum ether, (0.8 g), m.p. 140°; δ 1.1 (6H, d, $-\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.4 (3H, s, CH_3 , at position-4), 2.55–2.95 (5H, m, $\text{N}-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NHOH}$), 4.0 (2H, d of ArOCH_2), 6.21 (1H, s, proton at position-3) and 7.0–7.8 (3H, m, ArH).

Similarly, other compounds were prepared (Table 1).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. S. S. Lele and S. S. Madhava Rao for the microanalysis and nmr spectra.

References

1. B. N. C. PRICHARD and P. M. S. GILLAM, *Br. Med. J.*, 1964, 2, 727, *Am. J. Cardiol.*, 1966, 18, 887.

Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-Amino-4-(2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo/H-4'-n-butoxy-5'-nitrophen-1'-yl)-6-arylpyrimidines

M. D. ANKHIWALA

Department of Chemistry, R. R. Mehta College of Science, Palanpur-385 002

Manuscript received 24 December 1988, revised 10 March 1989, accepted 31 March 1989

2-AMINOPYRIMIDINES¹ are known for their physiological importance. With a view to get better therapeutic activity, some new 2-aminopyrimidines (2) were synthesised and evaluated for their antimicrobial activity. The compounds have been prepared² by the reaction of 2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-4'-n-butoxy-5'-nitrochalcones and 2'-hydroxy-4'-n-butoxy-5'-nitrochalcones (1) with guanidine nitrate in the presence of aqueous sodium hydroxide (40%) in ethanol (Scheme 1). Previously reported 2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-4'-n-butoxy-5'-nitrochalcones³ and 2'-hydroxy-4'-n-butoxy-5'-nitrochalcones⁴ have been prepared from 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-4-n-butoxy-5-nitroacetophenone or 2-hydroxy-4-n-butoxy-5-

nitroacetophenone and various araldehydes and evaluated their biological activity^{3,4}. The structure of the compounds has been supported by elemental analysis and ir spectral data. The products have been screened for their antimicrobial activity.

Antimicrobial activity: The compounds were screened for antibacterial and antifungal activities using cup-plate agar diffusion method⁵. The testing was carried out at a concentration of 50 μg using gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*, gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* and fungi *Aspergillus niger*. The compounds showed only mild antibacterial activity (inhibition 20–30%). The compounds 2 having bromo and chloro substituents in benzene ring were found to be more active. Maximum activity was observed in compounds (2) when R = 4-tolyl, 2- and 4-chlorophenyl, 2,4-dichlorophenyl against *S. aureus* and 2- and 4-bromophenyl, 4-methoxyphenyl against *E. coli*. The activity was not comparable with the known antibiotic like chloromycetin under similar condition. The most antifungal active compound of the series was Sl. no. 1 (Table 1); it inhibited the growth of *A. niger* to the extent of 80%. Most of the compounds showed moderate antifungal activity (inhibition 60–75%) and a few showed weak activity (inhibition < 55%) against *A. niger*. In general, the presence of chlorine atom in R decreased fungitoxicity.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The ir spectra